

Sample Information

Name	Sample 4	Data File Path	C:\Users\NRC\OneDrive\Desktop\Data\meat flavor HS-MS\19.D
Sample ID		Acq. Time (Local)	1/10/2022 4:37:16 PM (UTC+02:00)
Instrument	GCMS	Method Path (Acq)	D:\MassHunter\GCMS\2\methods\Oils_Volatile.M
MS Type	Q	Version (Acq SW)	MassHunter GC/MS Acquisition 10.0.368 14-Feb-2019 Copyright © 1989-2018 Agilent Technologies, Inc.
Inj. Vol. (ul)	1	IRM Status	
Position	4	Method Path (DA)	C:\Users\NRC\OneDrive\Desktop\Data\meat flavor HS-MS\19.D\Results\Qual\Version4\Oils_Volatile.M
Plate Pos.		Target Source Path	
Operator		Result Summary	

Sample Chromatograms

Chromatogram Peaks

Peak	Start	RT	End	Height	Area	Area %	SNR
1	4.226	4.357	4.426	3154854	10172857	28.26	
2	25.039	25.569	25.678	498190	6796686	18.88	
3	40.973	41.064	41.166	1254098	4717896	13.10	
4	44.492	44.652	44.755	7280200	36000846	100.00	
5	49.985	50.088	50.294	2103715	8296010	23.04	
6	51.896	51.982	52.079	1299925	5091326	14.14	
7	57.900	58.019	58.145	1470162	6802685	18.90	
8	64.719	64.897	65.028	761698	4322597	12.01	
9	65.978	66.024	66.093	3332782	7590684	21.08	
10	66.150	66.196	66.293	1294904	5209326	14.47	
11	68.410	68.479	68.587	4368832	15427465	42.85	
12	68.587	68.742	68.816	1052526	8634206	23.98	
13	68.816	68.868	68.925	1318485	5227690	14.52	
14	68.925	69.011	69.106	1008473	5005226	13.90	
15	71.631	71.740	71.914	3537797	17534796	48.71	
16	73.588	73.806	73.932	710651	5242365	14.56	
17	74.349	74.458	74.544	517121	4439175	12.33	
18	74.544	74.618	74.733	531064	4192016	11.64	

Chromatogram Peaks

Peak	Start	RT	End	Height	Area	Area %	SNR
1	4.260	4.357	4.432	1476835	4466962	21.01	
2	25.060	25.569	25.632	222445	2957425	13.91	
3	40.252	40.338	40.504	192586	705394	3.32	
4	40.973	41.064	41.219	405625	1524993	7.17	
5	44.488	44.652	44.801	4210635	21260671	100.00	
6	48.989	49.081	49.275	303728	1146294	5.39	
7	49.985	50.088	50.300	1320404	5136119	24.16	
8	51.902	51.971	52.074	244317	876116	4.12	
9	57.660	57.744	57.867	165116	627748	2.95	
10	62.976	63.060	63.260	146973	583596	2.74	
11	64.736	64.897	65.005	106179	497275	2.34	
12	65.978	66.024	66.098	657618	1410407	6.63	
13	67.506	67.575	67.675	230655	609156	2.87	
14	68.416	68.473	68.587	713250	2314846	10.89	
15	68.587	68.742	68.828	143908	1143215	5.38	
16	68.828	68.868	68.954	151585	555807	2.61	
17	71.631	71.740	71.946	648422	3001140	14.12	

Sample Spectra

Analysis Report

+ Scan (rt: 4.283-4.369 min) Peak 1 from + BPC Scan ((2R,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol; C5H12O2)

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
56.0300		10118	1.27					
60.0300		11146	1.40					
61.0400	1	563481	70.91					
62.0300	1	13569	1.71					
63.0100		110983	13.97					
70.0500		41417	5.21					
72.0700		10604	1.33					
73.0700	1	794616	100.00					
74.0700	1	57091	7.18					
75.0500	1	53130	6.69					
77.0200		12032	1.51					
78.0400		8510	1.07					
88.0500		17517	2.20					
91.0400		18601	2.34					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	(2R,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol	C5H12O2				997014-05-6	59.10	59.10			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	(2S,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol	C5H12O2				997014-05-5	56.66	56.66			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	3,3,5,5-Tetra deuteriomethoxycyclohexane	C7H10D4O				997021-68-1	52.08	52.08			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes (2R,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol	C5H12O2		997014-05-6	14.317		59.10	59.10			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 25.180-25.603 min)

Peak 2 from + BPC Scan (Geranic acid; C10H16O2)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0100		2159	1.91					
53.0400		8755	7.75					
54.0400		1794	1.59					
55.0400		3817	3.38					
65.0200		2321	2.06					
67.0400		7583	6.71					
68.0500		2886	2.56					
69.0700	1	112926	100.00					
70.0700	1	6516	5.77					
77.0200		3245	2.87					
79.0300		3460	3.06					
81.0500		3074	2.72					
82.0400		9206	8.15					
85.0100		3236	2.87					
91.0500		2739	2.43					
93.0500		1453	1.29					
100.0400		20641	18.28					
105.0400		1137	1.01					
107.0600		2016	1.79					
111.0100		2108	1.87					
122.0800		3571	3.16					
123.1000		15728	13.93					
124.0600		3354	2.97					
125.0400		7228	6.40					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID	Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes	LibSearch	Geranic acid	C10H16O2				459-80-3	58.80	58.80			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	2,6-Octadienoic acid, 3,7-dimethyl-, (Z)-	C10H16O2				4613-38-1	54.83	54.83			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	2,6-Octadienoic acid, 3,7-dimethyl-, (E)-	C10H16O2				4698-08-2	54.36	54.36			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	Neric acid	C10H16O2				4613-38-1	54.07	54.07			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	Methane, tetrafluoro-	CF4				75-73-0	51.17	51.17			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes	Geranic acid	C10H16O2	459-80-3	22.367		58.80	58.80			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Analysis Report

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 40.292-40.389 min) Peak 3 from + BPC Scan (Geranyl linalool isomer B; C20H34O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0100		2310	2.11					
53.0400		11782	10.75					
54.0200		2226	2.03					
55.0500		14205	12.96					
56.0200		1320	1.20					
57.0500		2069	1.89					
65.0200		3897	3.55					
66.0200		1328	1.21					
67.0500		14964	13.65					
68.0500		5860	5.35					
69.0700	1	109624	100.00					
70.0700	1	6678	6.09					
71.0400	1	3138	2.86					
77.0300		7584	6.92					
78.0200		1642	1.50					
79.0400		9144	8.34					
80.0400		4916	4.48					
81.0600		24603	22.44					
82.0500		6649	6.07					
83.0400		5959	5.44					
84.0500	1	59044	53.86					
85.0500	1	3856	3.52					
91.0400		11098	10.12					
92.0400		3336	3.04					
93.0600		12431	11.34					
94.0500		4008	3.66					
95.0600		10718	9.78					
96.0400		2132	1.94					
97.0500		2613	2.38					
105.0500		6963	6.35					
106.0400		1606	1.46					
107.0700		8110	7.40					
108.0600		4667	4.26					
109.0700		7934	7.24					
110.0400		2036	1.86					
115.0300		1412	1.29					
117.0300		2045	1.87					
119.0600		3077	2.81					
120.0500		1352	1.23					
121.0800		7246	6.61					
122.0600		2041	1.86					
123.1000		7560	6.90					
124.0900		2661	2.43					
131.0600		3713	3.39					
132.0200		1107	1.01					
133.0800		3970	3.62					
134.0600		2082	1.90					
135.0700		2703	2.47					
136.1100		9344	8.52					
137.1100		5476	5.00					
138.1000		1208	1.10					
139.0900		3126	2.85					
145.0600		1826	1.67					
146.0900		1258	1.15					
147.0900		1548	1.41					
149.1000		2930	2.67					
151.1000		1454	1.33					
159.1000		3637	3.32					
177.1200		2589	2.36					
187.1500		1939	1.77					
191.1300		1280	1.17					
202.1600		1580	1.44					
205.1400		1623	1.48					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O				0-00-0	69.21	69.21			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O				0-00-0	66.86	66.86			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2,6,10-Dodecatrienal, 3,7,11-trimethyl-, (Z,E)-	C15H24O				4380-32-9	65.51	65.51			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	3,7,11-Trimethyl-2,6,10-dodecatrien-1-ol	C15H24D2O				997283-78-4	65.48	65.48			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2,6,10-Dodecatrienal, 3,7,11-trimethyl-, (E,E)-	C15H24O				502-67-0	65.40	65.40			W11N17main.L
Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB	
Yes Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O		0-00-0			69.21	69.21			W11N17main.L	

Analysis Report

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 41.007-41.110 min) Peak 4 from + BPC Scan (Benzyl Benzoate; C14H12O2)

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
50.0300		5375	2.36					
51.0200		27582	12.12					
52.0300		3428	1.51					
63.0000		6003	2.64					
65.0300		22923	10.07					
74.0100		2863	1.26					
76.0300		3793	1.67					
77.0300		72351	31.79					
78.0300		8522	3.74					
79.0400		12926	5.68					
89.0300		12780	5.62					
90.0300		15373	6.75					
91.0500	1	110782	48.68					
92.0400	1	9145	4.02					
105.0200	1	227586	100.00					
106.0200	1	20148	8.85					
107.0400	1	13674	6.01					
165.0500		2769	1.22					
167.0800		14347	6.30					
194.0700	1	21819	9.59					
195.0600	1	3335	1.47					
212.1000	1	51666	22.70					
213.0900	1	8192	3.60					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Benzyl Benzoate	C14H12O2				120-51-4	75.18	75.18			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzyl Benzoate	C14H12O2				120-51-4	74.43	74.43			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzyl Benzoate	C14H12O2				120-51-4	73.53	73.53			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O2				120-51-4	72.60	72.60			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O2				120-51-4	72.16	72.16			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Benzyl Benzoate	C14H12O2		120-51-4	28.883		75.18	75.18			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 44.555-44.692 min) Peak 5 from + BPC Scan (Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester; C14H12O3)

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0300		43764	1.81					
53.0200		24775	1.03					
63.0200		74005	3.06					
64.0300		40927	1.69					
65.0400		295764	12.25					
77.0400		49834	2.06					
79.0400		26055	1.08					
89.0400		54766	2.27					
90.0500		26200	1.09					
91.0600	1	2414693	100.00					
92.0500	1	258209	10.69					
93.0300	1	48223	2.00					
120.0100		30492	1.26					
121.0200		80746	3.34					
228.1000	1	320671	13.28					
229.1000	1	49971	2.07					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3				118-58-1	72.29	72.29			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3				118-58-1	70.45	70.45			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3				118-58-1	70.28	70.28			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3				118-58-1	69.46	69.46			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	4-Benzyloxybenzoic acid	C14H12O3				1486-51-7	68.37	68.37			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3		118-58-1	32.567		72.29	72.29			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 49.029-49.132 min) Peak 6 from + BPC Scan (4'-Benzyloxy[1,2-13C2]phenylacetic acid; C15H14O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0100		4823	2.89					
52.0200		2907	1.74					
53.0200		3154	1.89					
55.0200		3449	2.06					
63.0100		3633	2.17					
65.0300		12628	7.56					
77.0300		3250	1.94					
79.0100		3934	2.35					
81.0200		3533	2.11					
89.0100		3277	1.96					
91.0400	1	167104	100.00					
92.0400	1	13708	8.20					
107.0000		5537	3.31					
107.9900		2404	1.44					
136.0000		3421	2.05					
137.0100		3016	1.80					
244.0800		13115	7.85					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	4'-Benzyloxy[1,2-13C2]phenylacetic acid	C15H14O3				997354-56-0	73.60	73.60			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Verimol K	C14H12O4				85985-75-7	71.45	71.45			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzyl (1,2,3-thiadiazol-4-yl)carbamate	C10H9N3O2S				997326-83-4	67.43	67.43			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	5-Hydroxy-7-(benzylseleno)-8-cyano-3-(ethoxycarbonyl)-4-(2-furyl)-2-methyl-1,6-naphthyridine	C24H19N3O4Se				997944-10-4	65.85	65.85			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	5-Amino-7-(benzylseleno)-8-cyano-3-(ethoxycarbonyl)-2-methyl-1,6-naphthyridine	C20H18N4O2Se				997874-23-9	64.88	64.88			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes 4'-Benzyloxy[1,2-13C2]phenylacetic acid	C15H14O3		997354-56-0			73.60	73.60			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 50.031-50.134 min) Peak 7 from + BPC Scan (Verimol K; C14H12O4)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0200		18691	2.48					
52.0300		12470	1.65					
53.0200		11772	1.56					
55.0200		8555	1.13					
63.0100		14401	1.91					
65.0300		56747	7.52					
77.0300		13626	1.81					
79.0300		16336	2.16					
81.0300		11504	1.52					
89.0300		13821	1.83					
90.0400		7707	1.02					
91.0500	1	754572	100.00					
92.0500	1	61022	8.09					
107.0100		22497	2.98					
108.0100		21747	2.88					
136.0100		10326	1.37					
137.0200		15359	2.04					
244.0800		48311	6.40					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Verimol K	C14H12O4				85985-75-7	72.77	72.77			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	4'-Benzyloxy[1,2-13C2]phenylacetic acid	C15H14O3				997354-56-0	71.83	71.83			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzyl (1,2,3-thiadiazol-4-yl)carbamate	C10H9N3O2S				997326-83-4	68.94	68.94			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	5-Hydroxy-7-(benzylseleno)-8-cyano-3-(ethoxycarbonyl)-4-(2-furyl)-2-methyl-1,6-naphthyridine	C24H19N3O4Se				997944-10-4	66.99	66.99			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	5-Amino-7-(benzylseleno)-8-cyano-3-(ethoxycarbonyl)-2-methyl-1,6-naphthyridine	C20H18N4O2Se				997874-23-9	66.00	66.00			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Verimol K	C14H12O4		85985-75-7	36.250		72.77	72.77			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 51.925-52.022 min) Peak 8 from + BPC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		3467	2.50					
54.0400		5008	3.61					
55.0600		40838	29.43					
56.0600		19726	14.21					
57.0700	1	138778	100.00					
58.0700	1	6342	4.57					
59.0000	1	2505	1.80					
66.0200		1582	1.14					
67.0400		13825	9.96					
68.0500		6216	4.48					
69.0600		24987	18.01					
70.0700		17204	12.40					
71.0800	1	104909	75.60					
72.0700	1	5906	4.26					
73.0200	1	1502	1.08					
74.0300		2651	1.91					
77.0200		3736	2.69					
78.0100		2068	1.49					
79.0400		14169	10.21					
80.0500		5815	4.19					
81.0500		8592	6.19					
82.0500		6604	4.76					
83.0700		17599	12.68					
84.0700		12100	8.72					
85.0900	1	77057	55.53					
86.0900	1	5093	3.67					
87.0200	1	3331	2.40					
91.0500		5923	4.27					
93.0500		7362	5.30					
94.0600		3380	2.44					
95.0700		9209	6.64					
96.0600		5205	3.75					
97.0800		14380	10.36					
98.0800		9230	6.65					
99.0900		24183	17.43					
105.0300		2223	1.60					
107.0500		3478	2.51					
108.0600		2048	1.48					
108.0900		3080	2.22					
109.0700		2813	2.03					
110.0600		2556	1.84					
111.0900		7437	5.36					
112.1000		6236	4.49					
113.1000		14610	10.53					
121.0700		3674	2.65					
122.0900		1496	1.08					
125.0900		3177	2.29					
126.1100		4856	3.50					
127.1200		9728	7.01					
135.0900		1583	1.14					
140.1300		3929	2.83					
141.1400		7182	5.17					
154.1500		3236	2.33					
155.1600		5151	3.71					
168.1700		2662	1.92					
169.1700		3754	2.71					
182.1700		2081	1.50					
183.1600		2366	1.71					
197.2300		2463	1.77					
225.2500		1520	1.10					
296.3400		3778	2.72					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	72.16	72.16			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6-pentamethylheptane	C12H25N3				997244-20-5	70.08	70.08			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	69.21	69.21			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	67.08	67.08			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99BO3				2665-11-4	65.23	65.23			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3		74764-11-7			72.16	72.16			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 57.687-57.796 min) Peak 9 from + BPC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0100		1658	1.78					
54.0400		2645	2.84					
55.0500		25205	27.04					
56.0600		13274	14.24					
57.0700	1	93210	100.00					
58.0700	1	4164	4.47					
67.0400		5290	5.68					
68.0400		3476	3.73					
69.0600		18363	19.70					
70.0600		11388	12.22					
71.0800	1	71042	76.22					
72.0700	1	3941	4.23					
72.9800	1	1405	1.51					
79.0300		2206	2.37					
81.0500		3976	4.27					
82.0500		4312	4.63					
83.0700		12753	13.68					
84.0800		7588	8.14					
85.0900	1	52285	56.09					
86.0800	1	3513	3.77					
91.0300		1990	2.14					
93.0500		1620	1.74					
95.0600		3474	3.73					
96.0600		2726	2.92					
97.0800		10982	11.78					
98.0800		5663	6.08					
99.1000	1	17137	18.39					
100.0800	1	1394	1.50					
105.0300		954	1.02					
107.0300		1433	1.54					
109.0600		2158	2.32					
110.0500		1575	1.69					
111.0900		5677	6.09					
112.0900		4250	4.56					
113.1000	1	10085	10.82					
114.0900	1	945	1.01					
121.0500		1336	1.43					
125.0900		2659	2.85					
126.1000		3376	3.62					
127.1200		6859	7.36					
140.1300		2456	2.64					
141.1400		5096	5.47					
154.1500		2280	2.45					
155.1600		3637	3.90					
168.1400		1846	1.98					
169.1700		2796	3.00					
183.1900		2033	2.18					
197.2200		1434	1.54					
211.2300		1466	1.57					
225.2400		1237	1.33					
239.2500		1212	1.30					
324.3700		2113	2.27					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	76.91	76.91			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6-pentamethylheptane	C12H25N3				997244-20-5	68.12	68.12			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	67.82	67.82			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99BO3				2665-11-4	67.11	67.11			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	66.62	66.62			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Iron, tricarbonyl[[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3		74764-11-7			76.91	76.91			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Analysis Report

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 63.008-63.117 min) Peak 10 from + BPC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C₂₁H₁₄FeN₂O₃)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0200		1444	1.68					
54.0300		2309	2.69					
55.0600		23726	27.59					
56.0600		11945	13.89					
57.0700	1	85982	100.00					
58.0700	1	4069	4.73					
67.0400		4701	5.47					
68.0400		3142	3.65					
69.0700		17200	20.00					
70.0600		10763	12.52					
71.0800	1	64218	74.69					
72.0800	1	3664	4.26					
73.0200	1	1233	1.43					
79.0200		2041	2.37					
81.0500		3874	4.51					
82.0600		4208	4.89					
83.0700		13028	15.15					
84.0800		7150	8.32					
85.0900	1	48355	56.24					
86.0800	1	3220	3.75					
91.0100		1743	2.03					
93.0400		1421	1.65					
95.0600		3032	3.53					
96.0400		2843	3.31					
97.0700		11700	13.61					
98.0800		5245	6.10					
99.1000	1	15910	18.50					
100.0700	1	1171	1.36					
105.0000		902	1.05					
107.0500		1018	1.18					
109.0800		1621	1.89					
110.0600		1574	1.83					
111.0900		6443	7.49					
112.0900		3850	4.48					
113.1100		9885	11.50					
123.0500		972	1.13					
124.0500		899	1.05					
125.1000		3081	3.58					
126.1100		3093	3.60					
127.1200		6717	7.81					
139.1200		1163	1.35					
140.1300		2414	2.81					
141.1400		4862	5.65					
154.1500		2048	2.38					
155.1500		3422	3.98					
168.1500		1562	1.82					
169.1700		2786	3.24					
182.1800		1355	1.58					
183.1700		2179	2.53					
196.2100		902	1.05					
197.1700		1040	1.21					
225.2400		1120	1.30					
352.3900		1061	1.23					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	76.94	76.94			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99B03				2665-11-4	70.99	70.99			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	68.86	68.86			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	68.68	68.68			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	4-Methyl-1-dodecanol	C13H27DO				86234-17-5	68.54	68.54			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Iron, tricarbonyl[[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3		74764-11-7			76.94	76.94			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 64.765-64.948 min) Peak 11 from + BPC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C₂₉H₄₈)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0100		1791	4.84					
54.0000		1151	3.11					
55.0500		17778	48.06					
56.0500		5419	14.65					
57.0600	1	32234	87.15					
58.0500	1	1932	5.22					
59.0100	1	816	2.21					
59.9800		1096	2.96					
67.0400		7050	19.06					
68.0300		2721	7.36					
69.0600		16445	44.46					
70.0600		5170	13.98					
71.0700	1	23117	62.50					
72.0700	1	1305	3.53					
73.0200	1	2330	6.30					
77.0200		2470	6.68					
79.0300		5723	15.47					
80.0400		1765	4.77					
81.0600		9574	25.88					
82.0500		3856	10.43					
83.0700	1	9251	25.01					
84.0200	1	922	2.49					
84.0800		2447	6.62					
85.0900	1	16363	44.24					
86.0500	1	1119	3.03					
88.0200		1366	3.69					
91.0400		6178	16.70					
92.0200		1395	3.77					
93.0500		6722	18.17					
94.0500		4078	11.02					
95.0600		10441	28.23					
96.0600		3281	8.87					
97.0800		8143	22.01					
98.0800		2658	7.19					
99.0800		5732	15.50					
101.0100		1006	2.72					
105.0400		7102	19.20					
106.0400		1672	4.52					
107.0600		6281	16.98					
108.0500		2613	7.06					
109.0800		7023	18.99					
110.0700		1913	5.17					
111.0800		5358	14.48					
112.0600		1244	3.36					
113.1000		3505	9.48					
115.0100		921	2.49					
117.0300		1686	4.56					
119.0600		6024	16.29					
120.0500		2015	5.45					
121.0700		5850	15.81					
122.0700		2566	6.94					
123.0800		4169	11.27					
124.0800		1182	3.20					
125.0900		2389	6.46					
126.1100		1117	3.02					
127.1100		2194	5.93					
128.0500		905	2.45					
129.0400		1574	4.26					
131.0300		1160	3.14					
131.0800		967	2.61					
133.0700		4366	11.80					
134.0600		2183	5.90					
135.0800		5800	15.68					
136.0900		3448	9.32					
137.1100		3749	10.14					
138.0800		815	2.20					
139.0600		856	2.31					
140.1200		895	2.42					
141.1200		2044	5.53					
143.0400		1052	2.85					
145.0700		2015	5.45					
147.0800		3939	10.65					
148.1100		1284	3.47					
149.0900		2999	8.11					
151.0800		1100	2.97					
155.1200		1162	3.14					
159.0400		863	2.33					
161.1100		2867	7.75					
162.1300		994	2.69					
163.1000		1172	3.17					
169.1500		1083	2.93					
173.0900		871	2.35					
175.1300		3946	10.67					
176.1100		1216	3.29					
177.1300		1214	3.28					
183.1600		878	2.37					
187.1000		954	2.58					
189.1500		6285	16.99					
190.1500		2819	7.62					
191.1500		1346	3.64					
203.1800	1	18188	49.17					
204.1800	1	3523	9.52					
205.1700	1	1785	4.83					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
207.1000	1	4706	12.72					
208.1100	1	1147	3.10					
218.2100	1	36988	100.00					
219.2100	1	6993	18.91					
281.1200		1068	2.89					
408.3400		973	2.63					
426.3800		835	2.26					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	70.72	70.72			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	64.66	64.66			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.beta.-Amyrin	C30H50O				559-70-6	57.74	57.74			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Nerolidol-epoxyacetate	C17H28O4				0-00-0	57.64	57.64			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.alpha.-Amyrin	C30H50O				638-95-9	55.38	55.38			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			70.72	70.72			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 66.001-66.053 min) Peak 12 from + BPC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0400		4859	1.22					
54.0400		9472	2.38					
55.0600		102298	25.69					
56.0600		54105	13.59					
57.0700	1	398186	100.00					
58.0700	1	17870	4.49					
67.0400		17704	4.45					
68.0600		13967	3.51					
69.0700		78214	19.64					
70.0700		48312	12.13					
71.0800	1	303152	76.13					
72.0900	1	16751	4.21					
79.0400		5509	1.38					
81.0500		14316	3.60					
82.0600		19026	4.78					
83.0700		63575	15.97					
84.0800		32008	8.04					
85.0900	1	228325	57.34					
86.0900	1	15120	3.80					
91.0300		4140	1.04					
93.0400		4412	1.11					
95.0700		11162	2.80					
96.0700		12905	3.24					
97.0800		56837	14.27					
98.0900		23789	5.97					
99.1000	1	77067	19.35					
100.1000	1	6159	1.55					
109.0600		5829	1.46					
110.0800		6654	1.67					
111.0900		30234	7.59					
112.1000		18467	4.64					
113.1100	1	48478	12.17					
114.1100	1	4347	1.09					
123.0900		4959	1.25					
124.1000		4353	1.09					
125.1100		15143	3.80					
126.1200		14847	3.73					
127.1200		33400	8.39					
139.1200		5445	1.37					
140.1400		11921	2.99					
141.1400		23842	5.99					
154.1700		9926	2.49					
155.1600		17513	4.40					
168.1800		8212	2.06					
169.1800		13737	3.45					
182.2000		6938	1.74					
183.2000		10578	2.66					
196.2200		5598	1.41					
197.2100		9188	2.31					
207.0300		6581	1.65					
210.2200		4894	1.23					
211.2400		7609	1.91					
224.2600		4120	1.03					
225.2700		6221	1.56					
239.2600		5713	1.43					
253.2600		5205	1.31					
267.2900		4065	1.02					
281.2300		6347	1.59					
380.4400		6277	1.58					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	77.78	77.78			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99BO3				2665-11-4	69.53	69.53			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	66.01	66.01			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideutero hexadecanol	C16H32D2O				56555-03-4	65.79	65.79			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	4-Methyl-1-dodecanol	C13H27DO				86234-17-5	65.57	65.57			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3		74764-11-7			77.78	77.78			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 67.540-67.609 min) Peak 13 from + BPC Scan (Geranyl linalool isomer B; C₂₀H₃₄O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0200		6194	4.39					
54.0300		1715	1.22					
55.0500		18088	12.82					
56.0400		3357	2.38					
57.0700		13355	9.46					
65.0000		1857	1.32					
67.0400		18139	12.85					
68.0500		17944	12.71					
69.0600	1	141147	100.00					
70.0700	1	9934	7.04					
71.0700	1	9485	6.72					
73.0200		3689	2.61					
77.0200		4644	3.29					
79.0400		9741	6.90					
80.0400		4417	3.13					
81.0600		78477	55.60					
82.0600		11629	8.24					
83.0600		9671	6.85					
84.0600		2376	1.68					
85.0700		6238	4.42					
91.0500		7981	5.65					
92.0400		3483	2.47					
93.0600		17698	12.54					
94.0600		7504	5.32					
95.0600		26300	18.63					
96.0600		5484	3.89					
97.0700		8222	5.82					
99.0700		3716	2.63					
100.0300		2124	1.50					
105.0400		6348	4.50					
106.0400		1965	1.39					
107.0700		11521	8.16					
108.0500		3946	2.80					
109.0900		14383	10.19					
110.0500		2755	1.95					
111.0800		4922	3.49					
113.0800		1577	1.12					
119.0600		6335	4.49					
120.0600		2159	1.53					
121.0800		17139	12.14					
122.0900		4960	3.51					
123.0900		14869	10.53					
124.0800		2672	1.89					
125.1000		2396	1.70					
133.0500		4562	3.23					
134.0700		3469	2.46					
135.0900		10523	7.46					
136.1100		16859	11.94					
137.1200	1	17629	12.49					
138.1200	1	2989	2.12					
141.0800		1632	1.16					
147.0900		4937	3.50					
148.0800		2144	1.52					
149.1200		10777	7.64					
151.0800		1561	1.11					
156.0700		1521	1.08					
161.1000		3457	2.45					
162.0900		1575	1.12					
163.1100		3149	2.23					
175.1300		3348	2.37					
177.1200		2796	1.98					
189.1400		3094	2.19					
191.1200		4070	2.88					
192.1700		2359	1.67					
203.1800		1865	1.32					
205.1700		1430	1.01					
207.0400	1	7257	5.14					
208.0300	1	1646	1.17					
253.0300		1437	1.02					
281.0400		3172	2.25					
341.2900		1839	1.30					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O				0-00-0	76.67	76.67			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O				0-00-0	75.40	75.40			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	72.10	72.10			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	3,7,11-Trimethyl-2,6,10-dodecatrien-1-ol	C15H24D2O				997283-78-4	71.10	71.10			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	3,7,11-Trimethyl-2,6,10-dodecatrien-1-ol	C15H24D2O				997283-78-5	67.33	67.33			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O		0-00-0			76.67	76.67			W11N17main.L

Analysis Report

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 68.433-68.519 min) Peak 14 from + BPC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0400		8820	2.17					
54.0500		12770	3.14					
55.0600		124698	30.66					
56.0600		57784	14.21					
57.0700	1	406718	100.00					
58.0800	1	18535	4.56					
67.0500	1	43769	10.76					
68.0600		26417	6.50					
69.0700		136669	33.60					
70.0700		54204	13.33					
71.0800	1	308642	75.89					
72.0900	1	17398	4.28					
73.0400	1	4386	1.08					
77.0200		8687	2.14					
79.0500		24828	6.10					
80.0400		18565	4.56					
81.0600		50059	12.31					
82.0700		35542	8.74					
83.0700		91360	22.46					
84.0800		35614	8.76					
85.0900	1	234474	57.65					
86.1000	1	15892	3.91					
91.0500		13690	3.37					
92.0500		7428	1.83					
93.0600		32581	8.01					
94.0600		11019	2.71					
95.0800		40471	9.95					
96.0800		20784	5.11					
97.0900		70624	17.36					
98.0900		25827	6.35					
99.1000	1	81779	20.11					
100.1000	1	6775	1.67					
105.0500		6625	1.63					
107.0700		8982	2.21					
108.0800		9660	2.37					
109.0800		15919	3.91					
110.0900		9960	2.45					
111.1000		36626	9.01					
112.1000		20180	4.96					
113.1100	1	51278	12.61					
114.1100	1	4741	1.17					
119.0500		4450	1.09					
121.0800		24180	5.95					
122.0800		4970	1.22					
123.1000		19844	4.88					
124.1100		6529	1.61					
125.1100		17659	4.34					
126.1200		15822	3.89					
127.1300		35546	8.74					
135.0900		6604	1.62					
136.1100		12831	3.15					
137.1100		8350	2.05					
138.1300		12115	2.98					
139.1200		8264	2.03					
140.1400		13111	3.22					
141.1600		25210	6.20					
153.1400		4171	1.03					
154.1600		11385	2.80					
155.1600		19098	4.70					
168.1700		8996	2.21					
169.1800		14980	3.68					
182.1800		7396	1.82					
183.2100		11713	2.88					
196.2100		6287	1.55					
197.2100		9953	2.45					
207.0400		7444	1.83					
210.2200		5315	1.31					
211.2400		8062	1.98					
224.2600		4170	1.03					
225.2600		6973	1.71					
239.2600		6154	1.51					
253.2400		6079	1.49					
267.2800		4999	1.23					
281.2200		7032	1.73					
295.3400		4316	1.06					
408.4800		5542	1.36					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	71.55	71.55			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99BO3				2665-11-4	70.45	70.45			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	68.01	68.01			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	67.61	67.61			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6-pentamethylheptane	C12H25N3				997244-20-5	66.24	66.24			W11N17main.L

Analysis Report

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes	Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3	74764-11-7			71.55	71.55			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 68.610-68.828 min) Peak 15 from + BPC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C29H48)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		4184	4.38					
54.0300		2497	2.61					
55.0500		28295	29.60					
56.0500		5103	5.34					
57.0700		18341	19.18					
58.0400		5805	6.07					
59.0400		6832	7.15					
59.9900		2403	2.51					
65.0200		2332	2.44					
67.0400		18157	18.99					
68.0500		8027	8.40					
69.0600		42025	43.96					
70.0600		5437	5.69					
71.0700		13375	13.99					
73.0200		3670	3.84					
77.0200		6746	7.06					
78.0200		2115	2.21					
79.0400		16431	17.19					
80.0500		9229	9.65					
81.0600		32297	33.78					
82.0600		10864	11.36					
83.0700		14703	15.38					
84.0600		3203	3.35					
85.0700		8244	8.62					
91.0400		14913	15.60					
92.0400		5246	5.49					
93.0600		26302	27.51					
94.0600		12292	12.86					
95.0700		30452	31.85					
96.0700		8334	8.72					
97.0800		10673	11.16					
98.0600		2481	2.59					
99.0700		2632	2.75					
105.0500		15450	16.16					
106.0500		3732	3.90					
107.0700		16379	17.13					
108.0700		6367	6.66					
109.0800		17895	18.72					
110.0700		3825	4.00					
111.0900		7192	7.52					
112.0700		1481	1.55					
115.0200		2050	2.14					
117.0400		3627	3.79					
119.0600		14829	15.51					
120.0600		4671	4.89					
121.0800		19399	20.29					
122.0800		6372	6.67					
123.1000		14518	15.19					
124.0800		2940	3.07					
125.0900		2981	3.12					
127.0700		1896	1.98					
128.0300		1622	1.70					
129.0300		2808	2.94					
131.0500		4864	5.09					
133.0700		11126	11.64					
134.0800		6160	6.44					
135.0900		14357	15.02					
136.1000		11180	11.69					
137.1200		10592	11.08					
138.1300		8328	8.71					
139.1100		2048	2.14					
141.0600		1658	1.73					
143.0800		1985	2.08					
145.0800		4800	5.02					
146.0700		1880	1.97					
147.1000		10195	10.66					
148.1100		3222	3.37					
149.1100		6324	6.61					
150.1000		1954	2.04					
151.1100		1610	1.68					
155.1000		1311	1.37					
157.0700		1850	1.94					
159.1000		3894	4.07					
161.1200		7457	7.80					
162.1000		2505	2.62					
163.1200		3833	4.01					
173.1000		2749	2.88					
175.1300		10358	10.83					
176.1300		2993	3.13					
177.1000		1780	1.86					
177.1500		1284	1.34					
187.1200		2568	2.69					
189.1500		18279	19.12					
190.1600		7037	7.36					
191.1300		4661	4.87					
203.1800	1	46422	48.56					
204.1900	1	9721	10.17					
205.1800	1	5033	5.26					
207.0500	1	7393	7.73					
208.0400	1	1662	1.74					
215.1700		1842	1.93					
218.2100	1	95603	100.00					
219.2200	1	17760	18.58					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
231.1900		1466	1.53					
253.0200		1432	1.50					
255.1800		1429	1.49					
257.2400		1568	1.64					
281.0700		3162	3.31					
365.3300		2340	2.45					
408.4100		2066	2.16					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	78.42	78.42			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	71.19	71.19			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	67.79	67.79			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O				0-00-0	65.21	65.21			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.beta.-Amyrin	C30H50O				559-70-6	62.55	62.55			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			78.42	78.42			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 68.828-68.931 min) Peak 16 from + BPC Scan (Geranyl linalool isomer; C20H34O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0100		2913	3.02					
52.0000		1488	1.54					
53.0300		10153	10.53					
54.0400		7564	7.84					
55.0500		35613	36.92					
56.0500		5903	6.12					
57.0700		17041	17.67					
58.0500		2781	2.88					
59.0400		3389	3.51					
60.0000		2830	2.93					
65.0200		5308	5.50					
66.0400		1972	2.04					
67.0500		40916	42.42					
68.0600		24948	25.86					
69.0700	1	96462	100.00					
70.0600	1	8478	8.79					
71.0600	1	11269	11.68					
73.0200		4651	4.82					
77.0200		14958	15.51					
78.0300		3783	3.92					
79.0400		28381	29.42					
80.0500		36039	37.36					
81.0600		49073	50.87					
82.0600		12278	12.73					
83.0700		15061	15.61					
84.0600		4130	4.28					
85.0700		7654	7.94					
91.0500		23664	24.53					
92.0500		21222	22.00					
93.0600		86020	89.18					
94.0600		18486	19.16					
95.0700		31016	32.15					
96.0600		9639	9.99					
97.0700		11708	12.14					
98.0600		3190	3.31					
99.0600		2909	3.02					
103.0200		1693	1.75					
105.0500		12483	12.94					
106.0300		2088	2.16					
107.0600		17735	18.39					
108.0700		6603	6.85					
109.0800		15099	15.65					
110.0700		4761	4.94					
111.0900		6769	7.02					
113.0600		1797	1.86					
115.0500		1711	1.77					
117.0600		2690	2.79					
119.0700		9910	10.27					
120.0700		3037	3.15					
121.0800		38368	39.78					
122.0800		6341	6.57					
123.1000		12462	12.92					
124.0900		3084	3.20					
125.0900		3167	3.28					
127.0700		1881	1.95					
129.0500		2498	2.59					
131.0600		3020	3.13					
133.0700		6463	6.70					
134.0800		3675	3.81					
135.0900		9581	9.93					
136.1100		25101	26.02					
137.1200		15876	16.46					
138.1000		3822	3.96					
139.1000		2192	2.27					
141.0700		1675	1.74					
145.0800		2774	2.88					
147.0900		5804	6.02					
148.0900		1914	1.98					
149.1100		4364	4.52					
150.0900		1786	1.85					
151.1100		2381	2.47					
154.1200		2421	2.51					
159.0900		2576	2.67					
161.1100		4116	4.27					
162.1100		1747	1.81					
163.1100		2773	2.87					
165.1000		1841	1.91					
173.1200		1966	2.04					
175.1300		5737	5.95					
176.1100		1511	1.57					
177.1000		2069	2.14					
187.1300		1504	1.56					
189.1500		6177	6.40					
190.1400		2876	2.98					
191.1200		2681	2.78					
203.1800	1	13258	13.74					
204.1600	1	2804	2.91					
205.1700	1	1859	1.93					
207.0400		7173	7.44					
209.0600		1597	1.66					
218.2100	1	24373	25.27					
219.2200	1	4632	4.80					
253.0300		1465	1.52					

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
279.2400	1	7566	7.84					
280.2500	1	2702	2.80					
281.0800	1	3425	3.55					
365.3700		2068	2.14					
393.3600	1	4597	4.77					
394.3700	1	1865	1.93					
408.3800		1948	2.02					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O			0-00-0		72.60	72.60			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O			0-00-0		72.14	72.14			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Duvatriendiol	C20H34O2			0-00-0		71.91	71.91			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O			0-00-0		70.80	70.80			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	RMDI, Cis,trans-	C15H22N2O2			17901-48-3		65.52	65.52			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O		0-00-0			72.60	72.60			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 71.677-71.815 min) Peak 17 from + BPC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		4443	1.29					
54.0500		8375	2.43					
55.0600		92281	26.73					
56.0700		47649	13.80					
57.0700	1	345211	100.00					
58.0700	1	16311	4.73					
67.0500		18957	5.49					
68.0500		14264	4.13					
69.0700		77053	22.32					
70.0700		43460	12.59					
71.0800	1	264999	76.76					
72.0800	1	14780	4.28					
79.0400		7642	2.21					
81.0600		19477	5.64					
82.0600		20162	5.84					
83.0800		66951	19.39					
84.0800		28976	8.39					
85.0900	1	201097	58.25					
86.0900	1	14201	4.11					
91.0400		8439	2.44					
93.0500		7496	2.17					
95.0700		13896	4.03					
96.0700		13781	3.99					
97.0800		61495	17.81					
98.0900		21821	6.32					
99.1000	1	71268	20.64					
100.0900	1	6463	1.87					
105.0500		7967	2.31					
107.0700		6749	1.95					
109.0800		8410	2.44					
110.0800		6994	2.03					
111.1000		32919	9.54					
112.1000		16865	4.89					
113.1100	1	43908	12.72					
114.1100	1	4061	1.18					
119.0600		4910	1.42					
121.0800		5946	1.72					
123.0900		5442	1.58					
124.1000		4637	1.34					
125.1100		16473	4.77					
126.1200		13705	3.97					
127.1300	1	31087	9.01					
128.0900	1	4847	1.40					
131.0600		3667	1.06					
133.0600		5204	1.51					
135.0800		5068	1.47					
138.1300		3714	1.08					
139.1200		6540	1.89					
140.1500		11087	3.21					
141.1400	1	24645	7.14					
142.1100	1	4289	1.24					
143.0700		3563	1.03					
145.0900		6472	1.87					
147.0900		7679	2.22					
153.1400		3861	1.12					
154.1600		9454	2.74					
155.1700		17136	4.96					
168.1700		7956	2.30					
169.1800		13053	3.78					
182.1900		6330	1.83					
183.1900		10520	3.05					
196.2100		5582	1.62					
197.2000		9096	2.63					
207.0500		7378	2.14					
210.2300		4672	1.35					
211.2400		7400	2.14					
224.2500		3814	1.10					
225.2600		5948	1.72					
239.2600		5517	1.60					
253.2300		5717	1.66					
267.2700		4683	1.36					
281.2300		5353	1.55					
295.3300		3658	1.06					
396.3900		6411	1.86					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	75.48	75.48			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99BO3				2665-11-4	70.06	70.06			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	67.52	67.52			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio hexadecanol	C16H32D2O				56555-03-4	66.02	66.02			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	65.96	65.96			W11N17main.L
Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB	
Yes Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3		74764-11-7			75.48	75.48			W11N17main.L	

Analysis Report

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 4.283-4.369 min) Peak 1 from + TIC Scan ((2R,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol; C5H12O2)

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
56.0300		10118	1.27					
60.0300		11146	1.40					
61.0400	1	563481	70.91					
62.0300	1	13569	1.71					
63.0100		110983	13.97					
70.0500		41417	5.21					
72.0700		10604	1.33					
73.0700	1	794616	100.00					
74.0700	1	57091	7.18					
75.0500	1	53130	6.69					
77.0200		12032	1.51					
78.0400		8510	1.07					
88.0500		17517	2.20					
91.0400		18601	2.34					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	(2R,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol	C5H12O2				997014-05-6	59.10	59.10			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	(2S,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol	C5H12O2				997014-05-5	56.66	56.66			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	3,3,5,5-Tetrauteriomethoxycyclohexane	C7H10D4O				997021-68-1	52.08	52.08			W11N17main.L
Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB	
Yes (2R,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol	C5H12O2		997014-05-6	14.317		59.10	59.10			W11N17main.L	

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 25.174-25.603 min) Peak 2 from + TIC Scan (Geranic acid; C10H16O2)

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0000		1742	1.56					
53.0400		8665	7.75					
54.0400		1776	1.59					
55.0400		3784	3.39					
65.0200		2299	2.06					
67.0400		7506	6.72					
68.0500		2832	2.53					
69.0700	1	111745	100.00					
70.0700	1	6449	5.77					
77.0200		3215	2.88					
79.0300		3427	3.07					
81.0500		3050	2.73					
82.0400		9117	8.16					
83.0300		1687	1.51					
84.9800		1196	1.07					
85.0300		2005	1.79					
91.0500		2714	2.43					
93.0500		1569	1.40					
100.0400		20421	18.27					
105.0400		1128	1.01					
107.0600		1998	1.79					
108.0600		1298	1.16					
109.0400		1197	1.07					
111.0100		2087	1.87					
122.0800		3531	3.16					
123.1000		15567	13.93					
124.0600		3320	2.97					
125.0400		7151	6.40					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes	LibSearch	Geranic acid	C10H16O2			459-80-3	57.32	57.32			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	2,6-Octadienoic acid, 3,7-dimethyl-, (E)-	C10H16O2			4698-08-2	56.01	56.01			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	3,7-Dimethyl-2E,6-octadienoic acid	C10H16O2			997115-70-0	55.33	55.33			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	2,6-Octadienoic acid, 3,7-dimethyl-, (Z)-	C10H16O2			4613-38-1	55.14	55.14			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	Neric acid	C10H16O2			4613-38-1	55.10	55.10			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes	Geranic acid	C10H16O2	459-80-3	22.367		57.32	57.32			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 41.007-41.110 min) Peak 3 from + TIC Scan (Benzyl Benzoate; C14H12O2)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
50.0300		5375	2.36					
51.0200		27582	12.12					
52.0300		3428	1.51					
63.0000		6003	2.64					
65.0300		22923	10.07					
74.0100		2863	1.26					
76.0300		3793	1.67					
77.0300		72351	31.79					
78.0300		8522	3.74					
79.0400		12926	5.68					
89.0300		12780	5.62					
90.0300		15373	6.75					
91.0500	1	110782	48.68					
92.0400	1	9145	4.02					
105.0200	1	227586	100.00					
106.0200	1	20148	8.85					
107.0400	1	13674	6.01					
165.0500		2769	1.22					
167.0800		14347	6.30					
194.0700	1	21819	9.59					
195.0600	1	3335	1.47					
212.1000	1	51666	22.70					
213.0900	1	8192	3.60					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Benzyl Benzoate	C14H12O2		105.0200		120-51-4	75.18	75.18			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzyl Benzoate	C14H12O2		105.0200		120-51-4	74.43	74.43			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzyl Benzoate	C14H12O2		105.0200		120-51-4	73.53	73.53			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O2		105.0200		120-51-4	72.60	72.60			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O2		105.0200		120-51-4	72.16	72.16			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Benzyl Benzoate	C14H12O2	105.0200	120-51-4	28.883		75.18	75.18			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 44.561-44.692 min)

Peak 4 from + TIC Scan (Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester; C14H12O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0300		45265	1.81					
53.0200		25602	1.03					
63.0200		76567	3.07					
64.0300		42369	1.70					
65.0400		306013	12.25					
77.0400		51583	2.07					
79.0400		26925	1.08					
89.0400		56678	2.27					
90.0500		27108	1.09					
91.0600	1	2497377	100.00					
92.0500	1	267021	10.69					
93.0300	1	49887	2.00					
120.0100		31544	1.26					
121.0200		83575	3.35					
228.1000	1	332235	13.30					
229.1000	1	51753	2.07					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3				118-58-1	72.29	72.29			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3				118-58-1	70.44	70.44			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3				118-58-1	70.28	70.28			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3				118-58-1	69.46	69.46			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	4-Benzyloxybenzoic acid	C14H12O3				1486-51-7	68.37	68.37			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3		118-58-1	32.567		72.29	72.29			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 50.031-50.140 min) Peak 5 from + TIC Scan (Verimol K; C14H12O4)

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0200		17926	2.48					
52.0300		11939	1.65					
53.0200		11307	1.56					
55.0200		8249	1.14					
63.0100		13828	1.91					
65.0300		54370	7.52					
77.0300		13125	1.82					
79.0300		15696	2.17					
81.0300		11077	1.53					
89.0300		13235	1.83					
90.0400		7384	1.02					
91.0500	1	723132	100.00					
92.0500	1	58451	8.08					
107.0100		21590	2.99					
108.0100		20871	2.89					
136.0200		9927	1.37					
137.0200		14718	2.04					
244.0800		46333	6.41					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Verimol K	C14H12O4				85985-75-7	72.77	72.77			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	4'-Benzyloxy[1,2- ¹³ C ₂]phenylacetic acid	C15H14O3				997354-56-0	71.83	71.83			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzyl (1,2,3-thiadiazol-4-yl)carbamate	C10H9N3O2S				997326-83-4	68.94	68.94			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	5-Hydroxy-7-(benzylseleno)-8-cyano-3-(ethoxycarbonyl)-4-(2'-furyl)-2-methyl-1,6-naphthyridine	C24H19N3O4Se				997944-10-4	66.97	66.97			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	5-Amino-7-(benzylseleno)-8-cyano-3-(ethoxycarbonyl)-2-methyl-1,6-naphthyridine	C20H18N4O2Se				997874-23-9	65.99	65.99			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Verimol K	C14H12O4		85985-75-7	36.250		72.77	72.77			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 51.925-52.034 min) Peak 6 from + TIC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0200		3273	2.58					
54.0400		4697	3.70					
55.0600		37924	29.87					
56.0600		18122	14.28					
57.0700	1	126949	100.00					
58.0700	1	5794	4.56					
59.0000	1	2438	1.92					
66.0200		1474	1.16					
67.0400		13228	10.42					
68.0500		5875	4.63					
69.0600		23244	18.31					
70.0700		15803	12.45					
71.0800	1	95918	75.56					
72.0700	1	5383	4.24					
73.0200	1	1473	1.16					
74.0300		2520	1.98					
77.0200		3643	2.87					
78.0100		2009	1.58					
79.0400		13675	10.77					
80.0500		5635	4.44					
81.0500		8281	6.52					
82.0500		6212	4.89					
83.0700		16301	12.84					
84.0700		11196	8.82					
85.0900	1	70476	55.52					
86.0900	1	4653	3.67					
87.0300	1	3249	2.56					
91.0500		5779	4.55					
93.0500		7166	5.64					
94.0600		3280	2.58					
95.0700		8904	7.01					
96.0500		4983	3.93					
97.0800		13363	10.53					
98.0800		8541	6.73					
99.0900		22130	17.43					
105.0400		2230	1.76					
107.0500		3400	2.68					
108.0500		2170	1.71					
108.0900		2772	2.18					
109.0700		2725	2.15					
110.0600		2416	1.90					
111.0900		6883	5.42					
112.1000		5717	4.50					
113.1000		13358	10.52					
121.0700		3620	2.85					
122.0900		1491	1.17					
123.0700		1319	1.04					
125.0900		2964	2.34					
126.1100		4460	3.51					
127.1200		8927	7.03					
135.0900		1523	1.20					
140.1300		3553	2.80					
141.1400		6589	5.19					
154.1500		2980	2.35					
155.1600		4702	3.70					
168.1700		2451	1.93					
169.1700		3397	2.68					
182.1700		1905	1.50					
183.1600		2192	1.73					
197.2300		2262	1.78					
225.2500		1368	1.08					
296.3400		3483	2.74					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[(N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N')-]	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	71.67	71.67			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6-pentamethylheptane	C12H25N3				997244-20-5	69.92	69.92			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	69.37	69.37			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	67.15	67.15			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99B03				2665-11-4	65.36	65.36			W11N17main.L
Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB	
Yes	Iron, tricarbonyl[(N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N')-]	C21H14FeN2O3	74764-11-7			71.67	71.67			W11N17main.L	

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 57.944-58.087 min) Peak 7 from + TIC Scan (2-Phenyl-2-phospha-bicyclo[3.2.0]hept-3-ene; C₁₂H₁₃P)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0300		9601	36.87					
52.0200		4848	18.62					
53.0300		13044	50.09					
54.0200		2853	10.96					
55.0400		9912	38.07					
57.0600		5505	21.14					
58.0200		2548	9.78					
59.0100		7595	29.17					
63.0100		5238	20.12					
64.0100		2864	11.00					
65.0200		8619	33.10					
66.0200		3076	11.81					
67.0300		6475	24.87					
68.0300		3488	13.39					
69.0400		11108	42.66					
71.0300		6913	26.55					
77.0300		15685	60.24					
78.0400		7099	27.26					
79.0300		9074	34.85					
80.0200		3270	12.56					
81.0400		8316	31.94					
82.0400		3233	12.42					
83.0500		4363	16.76					
85.0400		4984	19.14					
89.0200		4129	15.86					
91.0400		12530	48.12					
92.0300		3164	12.15					
94.0100		3444	13.23					
95.0400		7404	28.44					
97.0300		7042	27.04					
102.0300		3179	12.21					
103.0300		6130	23.54					
104.0300		2504	9.62					
105.0400		11418	43.85					
107.0300		6466	24.83					
108.0200		2978	11.44					
109.0400		4805	18.45					
111.0400		2577	9.90					
115.0400		17962	68.98					
116.0400		4709	18.09					
117.0400		7279	27.95					
118.0300		2480	9.52					
119.0300		3343	12.84					
121.0300		6236	23.95					
122.0300		3232	12.41					
123.0400		6041	23.20					
127.0400		8999	34.56					
128.0500		16253	62.42					
129.0400		13437	51.61					
130.0400		2717	10.44					
131.0300		9914	38.07					
132.0400		5044	19.37					
133.0400		7754	29.78					
134.0200		3174	12.19					
135.0400		3559	13.67					
136.0400		11074	42.53					
137.0600		2563	9.84					
139.0400	1	22283	85.58					
140.0300	1	2633	10.11					
145.0500		12633	48.52					
146.0500		3336	12.81					
147.0400		3723	14.30					
149.0400		3554	13.65					
150.0300		3984	15.30					
156.0500		2747	10.55					
157.0500		7410	28.46					
158.0400		2897	11.13					
159.0400		3529	13.55					
160.0500		26038	100.00					
161.0600		12131	46.59					
162.0300		3179	12.21					
163.0700		2561	9.84					
165.0500		14120	54.23					
173.0500		11161	42.86					
174.0700		4010	15.40					
175.0700		2524	9.69					
184.0400		3699	14.20					
185.0500		6193	23.78					
187.0400		2653	10.19					
188.0300		3065	11.77					
189.0600		4567	17.54					
193.0500	1	19021	73.05					
194.0500	1	2600	9.98					
201.0500		24900	95.63					
202.0600	1	10909	41.89					
203.0700	1	2585	9.93					
212.0500		4453	17.10					
213.0500		4376	16.81					
215.0600		3327	12.78					
229.0600		22366	85.90					
230.0600	1	21546	82.75					
231.0800	1	4106	15.77					
240.0400		3140	12.06					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
244.0600		2650	10.18					
258.0600		9804	37.65					
259.0600		6781	26.04					
261.0800		7503	28.81					
262.0800		3050	11.71					
272.0600		4254	16.34					
290.0900		7979	30.64					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	2-Phenyl-2-phosphabicyclo[3.2.0]hept-3-ene	C12H13P				997170-02-4	50.02	50.02			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes 2-Phenyl-2-phosphabicyclo[3.2.0]hept-3-ene	C12H13P		997170-02-4			50.02	50.02			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 64.759-64.977 min) Peak 8 from + TIC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C29H48)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0100		1706	5.09					
54.0000		1084	3.23					
55.0500		16656	49.68					
56.0500		4973	14.83					
57.0600	1	29052	86.65					
58.0500	1	1774	5.29					
59.0100	1	774	2.31					
65.0000		710	2.12					
67.0400		6691	19.96					
68.0300		2597	7.75					
69.0600		15295	45.62					
70.0600		4776	14.24					
71.0700	1	20769	61.94					
72.0900	1	838	2.50					
73.0100	1	2299	6.86					
77.0200		2354	7.02					
79.0300		5408	16.13					
80.0300		1695	5.06					
81.0600		9069	27.05					
82.0500		3660	10.92					
83.0700		8691	25.92					
84.0700		2772	8.27					
85.0900	1	14681	43.79					
86.0500	1	986	2.94					
88.0200		1172	3.49					
91.0400		5843	17.43					
92.0200		1332	3.97					
93.0500		6266	18.69					
94.0500		3823	11.40					
95.0600		9840	29.35					
96.0600		3161	9.43					
97.0800		7692	22.94					
98.0800		2479	7.39					
99.0800		5164	15.40					
101.0100		887	2.65					
105.0400		6641	19.81					
106.0400		1576	4.70					
107.0600		5823	17.37					
108.0500		2437	7.27					
109.0800		6641	19.81					
110.0700		1802	5.37					
111.0800		5066	15.11					
112.0500		1208	3.60					
113.1000		3147	9.39					
115.0100		951	2.84					
117.0200		1601	4.77					
119.0600		5594	16.68					
120.0400		1881	5.61					
121.0700		5483	16.35					
122.0700		2314	6.90					
123.0800		3971	11.84					
124.0800		1125	3.36					
125.0900		2297	6.85					
126.1300		681	2.03					
127.1100		1786	5.33					
128.0100		790	2.36					
129.0400		1523	4.54					
131.0300		1093	3.26					
131.0800		925	2.76					
133.0600		4061	12.11					
134.0700		1507	4.49					
135.0800		5437	16.22					
136.0900		3185	9.50					
137.1100		3496	10.43					
138.0800		764	2.28					
139.0600		825	2.46					
141.1200		1853	5.53					
143.0500		833	2.48					
145.0700		1899	5.66					
147.0800		3688	11.00					
148.1100		1156	3.45					
149.0900		2827	8.43					
153.1000		647	1.93					
155.1200		1057	3.15					
157.0900		703	2.10					
159.0500		772	2.30					
159.1100		721	2.15					
161.1100		2655	7.92					
162.1300		888	2.65					
163.1000		1152	3.44					
165.1000		693	2.07					
169.1500		1010	3.01					
173.1000		795	2.37					
175.1000		1178	3.51					
175.1500		2475	7.38					
176.1100		1117	3.33					
177.1200		1066	3.18					
189.1500		5765	17.20					
190.1500		2599	7.75					
191.1300		1607	4.79					
203.1800	1	16540	49.33					
204.1700	1	3387	10.10					
205.1700	1	1674	4.99					

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
207.1000	1	4539	13.54					
208.1100	1	1060	3.16					
218.2100	1	33529	100.00					
219.2000	1	6336	18.90					
281.1100		1032	3.08					
408.3400		929	2.77					
426.3700		720	2.15					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	70.89	70.89			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	64.59	64.59			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.beta.-Amyrin	C30H50O				559-70-6	57.67	57.67			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Nerolidol-epoxyacetate	C17H28O4				0-00-0	57.13	57.13			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Proceroleanol-A (olean-13(18)-en-9.alpha.-ol)	C30H50O				0-00-0	55.64	55.64			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			70.89	70.89			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 65.995-66.058 min) Peak 9 from + TIC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0400		4388	1.28					
54.0400		8365	2.43					
55.0600		89736	26.10					
56.0600		47037	13.68					
57.0700	1	343864	100.00					
58.0700	1	15522	4.51					
67.0400		16187	4.71					
68.0600		12451	3.62					
69.0700		68803	20.01					
70.0700		42045	12.23					
71.0800	1	261513	76.05					
72.0800	1	14451	4.20					
73.0300	1	3769	1.10					
79.0400		5342	1.55					
81.0500		13529	3.93					
82.0600		17126	4.98					
83.0700		55634	16.18					
84.0800		27831	8.09					
85.0900	1	196926	57.27					
86.0900	1	13023	3.79					
91.0300		4136	1.20					
93.0500		4331	1.26					
95.0600		10786	3.14					
96.0700		11642	3.39					
97.0800		49781	14.48					
98.0900		20809	6.05					
99.1000	1	66495	19.34					
100.1000	1	5350	1.56					
109.0600		5765	1.68					
110.0800		6009	1.75					
111.0900		26594	7.73					
112.1000		16012	4.66					
113.1100	1	41857	12.17					
114.1100	1	3709	1.08					
123.0900		4974	1.45					
124.1100		4003	1.16					
125.1100		13329	3.88					
126.1200		12848	3.74					
127.1200		28820	8.38					
135.0500		3518	1.02					
139.1200		4815	1.40					
140.1400		10287	2.99					
141.1400		20591	5.99					
154.1700		8584	2.50					
155.1600		15160	4.41					
168.1700		7129	2.07					
169.1800		11819	3.44					
182.1900		5997	1.74					
183.2000		8979	2.61					
196.2200		4852	1.41					
197.2100		7942	2.31					
207.0400		6547	1.90					
210.2200		4143	1.20					
211.2400		6590	1.92					
224.2600		3501	1.02					
225.2700		4959	1.44					
239.2500		4984	1.45					
253.2600		4337	1.26					
281.2300		5289	1.54					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	78.61	78.61			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99BO3				2665-11-4	70.57	70.57			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	67.81	67.81			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideutero hexadecanol	C16H32D2O				56555-03-4	67.22	67.22			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	4-Methyl-1-dodecanol	C13H27DO				86234-17-5	66.23	66.23			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3		74764-11-7			78.61	78.61			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 66.156-66.293 min) Peak 10 from + TIC Scan (Geranyl linalool isomer; C₂₀H₃₄O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		3659	6.43					
54.0300		2653	4.66					
55.0500		33672	59.18					
56.0600		7346	12.91					
57.0700		26938	47.34					
58.0400		11603	20.39					
59.0400		11681	20.53					
60.0300		1529	2.69					
65.0200		1381	2.43					
67.0400		19232	33.80					
68.0500		9768	17.17					
69.0700		56901	100.00					
70.0700		7835	13.77					
71.0600		18463	32.45					
73.0200		4419	7.77					
77.0100		3750	6.59					
78.0200		1247	2.19					
79.0400		9603	16.88					
80.0400		8757	15.39					
81.0600		49679	87.31					
82.0600		26594	46.74					
83.0700		22654	39.81					
84.0600		4153	7.30					
85.0800		10162	17.86					
91.0400		7975	14.02					
92.0400		2764	4.86					
93.0600		15191	26.70					
94.0600		6868	12.07					
95.0700		46620	81.93					
96.0700		14343	25.21					
97.0800		12677	22.28					
98.0700		3216	5.65					
99.0800		2966	5.21					
100.0600		1041	1.83					
105.0400		7016	12.33					
106.0500		1867	3.28					
107.0700		12834	22.56					
108.0800		3891	6.84					
109.0800		22795	40.06					
110.0800		5984	10.52					
111.0800		6732	11.83					
112.0700		1685	2.96					
113.0700		1924	3.38					
115.0200		1544	2.71					
117.0300		1245	2.19					
119.0500		6734	11.84					
120.0600		2276	4.00					
121.0700		13166	23.14					
122.0800		4290	7.54					
123.1000		33804	59.41					
124.0900		5695	10.01					
125.0900		3343	5.87					
127.0900		1015	1.78					
129.0500		1596	2.81					
131.0400		1898	3.34					
133.0700		5450	9.58					
134.0700		2937	5.16					
135.0800		8173	14.36					
136.0900		5643	9.92					
137.1100		7080	12.44					
138.1300	1	26557	46.67					
139.1100	1	4456	7.83					
141.1000		1229	2.16					
145.0600		2017	3.54					
147.0800		4877	8.57					
148.0900		1932	3.40					
149.1000		6336	11.13					
150.1100		1968	3.46					
151.0800		1193	2.10					
159.0700		1620	2.85					
161.1100		4934	8.67					
162.1100		1928	3.39					
163.1200	1	7440	13.07					
164.1300	1	1370	2.41					
165.0900		1547	2.72					
173.1200		1937	3.40					
175.1300		3704	6.51					
177.1400		3292	5.79					
179.1000		1020	1.79					
187.1300		1081	1.90					
189.1400		2805	4.93					
190.1200		1140	2.00					
191.1300		4087	7.18					
203.1500		1692	2.97					
205.2000		1552	2.73					
207.0500	1	7138	12.55					
208.0400	1	1659	2.92					
209.0500	1	1326	2.33					
217.1900		1165	2.05					
218.1900		1688	2.97					
221.1600		2401	4.22					
239.2200		1667	2.93					
253.0100		1444	2.54					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
257.2100		1138	2.00					
259.1800		1092	1.92					
274.2700		2630	4.62					
281.0500		2909	5.11					
287.2800	1	4032	7.09					
288.2500	1	1114	1.96					
297.2500		1033	1.82					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O			0-00-0		73.72	73.72			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O			0-00-0		73.38	73.38			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O			0-00-0		72.71	72.71			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	3,7,11-Trimethyl-2,6,10-dodecatrien-1-ol	C15H24D2O			997283-78-5		70.26	70.26			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	(4aR,9aS,9bS)-4a,6,6,9a-tetramethyl-trans-perhydroindano[2,1-c]pyran	C16H28O			0-00-0		68.47	68.47			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O		0-00-0			73.72	73.72			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 68.433-68.530 min) Peak 11 from + TIC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0400		8370	2.27					
54.0500		11891	3.22					
55.0600		114813	31.13					
56.0600		52607	14.27					
57.0700	1	368765	100.00					
58.0800	1	16817	4.56					
65.0200		3718	1.01					
67.0500		41512	11.26					
68.0600		25030	6.79					
69.0700		127365	34.54					
70.0700		49503	13.42					
71.0800	1	279397	75.77					
72.0900	1	15778	4.28					
73.0300	1	4336	1.18					
77.0300		8419	2.28					
79.0500		23694	6.43					
80.0400		18205	4.94					
81.0600		47763	12.95					
82.0700		33156	8.99					
83.0700		84010	22.78					
84.0800		32510	8.82					
85.0900	1	212270	57.56					
86.1000	1	14390	3.90					
91.0500		13368	3.63					
92.0500		7475	2.03					
93.0600		32321	8.76					
94.0600		10725	2.91					
95.0800		38406	10.41					
96.0800		19476	5.28					
97.0900		64793	17.57					
98.0900		23622	6.41					
99.1000	1	74148	20.11					
100.1000	1	6099	1.65					
105.0500		6417	1.74					
107.0700		8728	2.37					
108.0800		9080	2.46					
109.0800		15185	4.12					
110.0900		9320	2.53					
111.1000		33614	9.12					
112.1000		18370	4.98					
113.1100	1	46426	12.59					
114.1100	1	4315	1.17					
119.0500		4321	1.17					
121.0800		23395	6.34					
122.0800		4780	1.30					
123.1000		18723	5.08					
124.1100		5969	1.62					
125.1100		16233	4.40					
126.1200		14386	3.90					
127.1300		32231	8.74					
133.0500		3705	1.00					
135.0900		6397	1.73					
136.1100		12561	3.41					
137.1000		8140	2.21					
138.1300		11432	3.10					
139.1200		7644	2.07					
140.1400		11907	3.23					
141.1600		22852	6.20					
153.1400		3788	1.03					
154.1600		10395	2.82					
155.1600		17350	4.70					
168.1700		8160	2.21					
169.1800		13540	3.67					
182.1800		6719	1.82					
183.2100		10634	2.88					
196.2100		5718	1.55					
197.2100		9037	2.45					
207.0400		7430	2.01					
210.2200		4773	1.29					
211.2400		7280	1.97					
224.2600		3706	1.01					
225.2600		6315	1.71					
239.2600		5526	1.50					
253.2400		5403	1.47					
267.2800		4525	1.23					
281.2200		6251	1.70					
295.3400		3917	1.06					
408.4800		4926	1.34					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	71.19	71.19			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99BO3				2665-11-4	70.32	70.32			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	68.09	68.09			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	67.52	67.52			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6-pentamethylheptane	C12H25N3				997244-20-5	66.39	66.39			W11N17main.L

Analysis Report

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes	Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3	74764-11-7			71.19	71.19			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 68.610-68.816 min) Peak 12 from + TIC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C29H48)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		4156	4.27					
54.0300		2448	2.51					
55.0500		28404	29.17					
56.0500		5141	5.28					
57.0700		18565	19.06					
58.0300		5902	6.06					
59.0400		6957	7.14					
59.9900		2404	2.47					
65.0200		2299	2.36					
67.0400		17964	18.45					
68.0500		7901	8.11					
69.0600		41676	42.79					
70.0600		5456	5.60					
71.0700		13558	13.92					
73.0200		3683	3.78					
77.0200		6686	6.86					
78.0200		2101	2.16					
79.0400		16470	16.91					
80.0500		8947	9.19					
81.0600		32462	33.33					
82.0600		11011	11.31					
83.0700		14893	15.29					
84.0600		3221	3.31					
85.0700		8341	8.56					
91.0400		14924	15.32					
92.0400		5047	5.18					
93.0600		25727	26.42					
94.0600		12343	12.67					
95.0700		30758	31.58					
96.0700		8421	8.65					
97.0800		10789	11.08					
98.0600		2497	2.56					
99.0700		2637	2.71					
105.0500		15602	16.02					
106.0500		3777	3.88					
107.0700		16499	16.94					
108.0700		6425	6.60					
109.0800		18113	18.60					
110.0700		3857	3.96					
111.0900		7243	7.44					
112.0700		1481	1.52					
115.0200		2062	2.12					
117.0400		3666	3.76					
119.0600		15005	15.41					
120.0600		4719	4.85					
121.0800		19290	19.81					
122.0800		6421	6.59					
123.1000		14748	15.14					
124.0800		2967	3.05					
125.0900		2994	3.07					
127.0700		1895	1.95					
128.0400		1633	1.68					
129.0300		2830	2.91					
131.0500		4903	5.03					
133.0700		11267	11.57					
134.0800		6246	6.41					
135.0900		14508	14.90					
136.1000		11115	11.41					
137.1200		10598	10.88					
138.1300		8594	8.82					
139.1100		2118	2.18					
141.0600		1689	1.73					
143.0800		2041	2.10					
145.0800		4869	5.00					
146.0700		1897	1.95					
147.1000		10311	10.59					
148.1100		3312	3.40					
149.1100		6395	6.57					
150.1000		1964	2.02					
151.1000		1651	1.70					
155.1000		1343	1.38					
157.0700		1903	1.95					
159.1000		3933	4.04					
161.1200		7546	7.75					
162.1000		2493	2.56					
163.1200		3869	3.97					
173.1000		2777	2.85					
175.1300		10463	10.74					
176.1300		3029	3.11					
177.1000		1734	1.78					
177.1500		1354	1.39					
187.1200		2595	2.66					
189.1500		18544	19.04					
190.1600		7139	7.33					
191.1300		4692	4.82					
203.1800	1	47313	48.58					
204.1900	1	9897	10.16					
205.1800	1	5111	5.25					
207.0500	1	7429	7.63					
208.0400	1	1679	1.72					
215.1700		1856	1.91					
218.2100	1	97388	100.00					
219.2200	1	18122	18.61					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
231.1900		1483	1.52					
253.0200		1433	1.47					
255.1800		1456	1.49					
257.2400		1610	1.65					
281.0700		3166	3.25					
365.3300		2308	2.37					
408.4100		1993	2.05					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	78.46	78.46			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	71.23	71.23			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	67.64	67.64			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O				0-00-0	65.03	65.03			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.beta.-Amyrin	C30H50O				559-70-6	62.63	62.63			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			78.46	78.46			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 68.816-68.925 min) Peak 13 from + TIC Scan (Geranyl linalool isomer; C20H34O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0100		2823	3.00					
52.0000		1442	1.53					
53.0300		9860	10.48					
54.0400		7306	7.77					
55.0500		35149	37.37					
56.0600		5815	6.18					
57.0700		16837	17.90					
58.0400		3246	3.45					
59.0400		3586	3.81					
60.0000		2804	2.98					
65.0200		5143	5.47					
66.0200		2827	3.01					
67.0500		39881	42.40					
68.0600		24067	25.59					
69.0700	1	94056	100.00					
70.0600	1	8336	8.86					
71.0600	1	11278	11.99					
73.0200		4554	4.84					
77.0200		14572	15.49					
78.0300		3720	3.96					
79.0400		27771	29.53					
80.0500		34894	37.10					
81.0600		48335	51.39					
82.0600		12055	12.82					
83.0700		14868	15.81					
84.0600		4009	4.26					
85.0700		7546	8.02					
91.0500		23213	24.68					
92.0500		20480	21.77					
93.0600		83488	88.76					
94.0600		18324	19.48					
95.0700		30872	32.82					
96.0700		9490	10.09					
97.0700		11560	12.29					
98.0600		3123	3.32					
99.0600		2851	3.03					
103.0200		1689	1.80					
105.0500		12637	13.44					
106.0500		3253	3.46					
107.0600		17707	18.83					
108.0700		6608	7.03					
109.0800		15188	16.15					
110.0700		4689	4.99					
111.0900		6809	7.24					
112.0500		1553	1.65					
113.0600		1772	1.88					
115.0500		1720	1.83					
117.0500		2718	2.89					
119.0700		10131	10.77					
120.0600		3103	3.30					
121.0800		37533	39.91					
122.0800		6365	6.77					
123.0900		12497	13.29					
124.0800		3067	3.26					
125.0900		3121	3.32					
127.0700		1871	1.99					
129.0400		2489	2.65					
131.0600		3082	3.28					
133.0700		6703	7.13					
134.0800		3765	4.00					
135.0900		9803	10.42					
136.1100		24474	26.02					
137.1200		15700	16.69					
138.1000		3876	4.12					
139.1000		2172	2.31					
145.0800		2870	3.05					
147.0900		6038	6.42					
148.0900		2042	2.17					
149.1100		4466	4.75					
150.0900		1838	1.95					
151.1100		2358	2.51					
154.1100		2358	2.51					
159.0900		2599	2.76					
161.1100		4277	4.55					
162.1100		1721	1.83					
163.1100		2851	3.03					
165.1000		1827	1.94					
173.1200		2002	2.13					
175.1300		5832	6.20					
176.1100		1556	1.65					
177.1000		2153	2.29					
187.1300		1540	1.64					
189.1600		7063	7.51					
190.1500		3085	3.28					
191.1200		2855	3.04					
203.1800	1	15657	16.65					
204.1700	1	3262	3.47					
205.1700	1	2091	2.22					
207.0400		7152	7.60					
209.0600		1593	1.69					
218.2100	1	29492	31.36					
219.2100	1	5507	5.85					
253.0300		1421	1.51					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
279.2400	1	7338	7.80					
280.2200	1	1450	1.54					
281.0800	1	3401	3.62					
365.3200		1634	1.74					
393.3600	1	4584	4.87					
394.3700	1	1914	2.04					
408.3800		2105	2.24					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O				0-00-0	72.45	72.45			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Duvatriendiol	C20H34O2				0-00-0	71.98	71.98			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O				0-00-0	71.82	71.82			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	71.06	71.06			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	RMDI, Cis,trans-	C15H22N2O2				17901-48-3	65.36	65.36			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O		0-00-0			72.45	72.45			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 68.925-69.079 min) Peak 14 from + TIC Scan (Geranyl linalool isomer; C20H34O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0100		1820	3.35					
53.0300		6685	12.29					
54.0300		3606	6.63					
55.0500		25818	47.45					
56.0500		4335	7.97					
57.0600		13502	24.82					
58.0300		1835	3.37					
59.0300		1976	3.63					
59.9900		2119	3.90					
65.0100		3854	7.08					
66.0200		2198	4.04					
67.0400		25077	46.09					
68.0500		13073	24.03					
69.0600		54408	100.00					
70.0600		5578	10.25					
71.0700		8769	16.12					
73.0300		4390	8.07					
74.0200		2355	4.33					
77.0200		11620	21.36					
78.0200		3712	6.82					
79.0400		25837	47.49					
80.0500		16493	30.31					
81.0600		30396	55.87					
82.0600		7736	14.22					
83.0700		11036	20.28					
84.0500		3045	5.60					
85.0800		6032	11.09					
87.0100		2433	4.47					
91.0500		20524	37.72					
92.0500		10297	18.93					
93.0600		48714	89.53					
94.0600		10493	19.29					
95.0700		23670	43.50					
96.0600		6257	11.50					
97.0700		8683	15.96					
98.0700		2413	4.43					
99.0700		2361	4.34					
103.0100		1394	2.56					
105.0500		13167	24.20					
106.0500		3448	6.34					
107.0700		16834	30.94					
108.0700		7751	14.25					
109.0800		11704	21.51					
110.0700		2997	5.51					
111.0900		5030	9.24					
115.0300		2037	3.74					
117.0300		3025	5.56					
119.0600		10663	19.60					
120.0600		3155	5.80					
121.0800		28672	52.70					
122.0800		5041	9.26					
123.0900		8257	15.18					
124.0800		1939	3.56					
125.0900		2703	4.97					
129.0400		2652	4.87					
131.0500		3522	6.47					
133.0700		7833	14.40					
134.0800		5033	9.25					
135.1000		14509	26.67					
136.1100		15252	28.03					
137.1100		9494	17.45					
138.1100		2578	4.74					
139.1100		1519	2.79					
145.0800		3405	6.26					
147.0900		7340	13.49					
148.0900		2096	3.85					
149.1000		5021	9.23					
150.1300		2041	3.75					
151.1000		1829	3.36					
159.1100		3610	6.63					
161.1200		7612	13.99					
162.1100		1932	3.55					
163.1000		1876	3.45					
165.0900		1444	2.65					
173.1300		2522	4.64					
175.1400	1	8430	15.49					
176.1300	1	1933	3.55					
177.1000		1527	2.81					
187.1300		1879	3.45					
189.1400		5150	9.46					
190.1600		2745	5.05					
191.1100		2420	4.45					
203.1700		5289	9.72					
204.1600		1682	3.09					
207.0400	1	7204	13.24					
208.0600	1	1643	3.02					
209.0600	1	1389	2.55					
218.2100		5068	9.32					
229.1700		1995	3.67					
231.2000		2007	3.69					
253.0400		1598	2.94					
257.2000		1579	2.90					
270.2100		1854	3.41					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
271.2200		2271	4.17					
277.2300		5244	9.64					
281.0600		3372	6.20					
365.3400	1	19720	36.25					
366.3400	1	6110	11.23					
393.3600		3248	5.97					
408.3800		2951	5.42					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O				0-00-0	70.26	70.26			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Duvatriendiol	C20H34O2				0-00-0	69.74	69.74			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	69.11	69.11			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O				0-00-0	68.50	68.50			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Hexadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester	C17H28O2				37822-81-4	62.14	62.14			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O		0-00-0			70.26	70.26			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 71.677-71.826 min) Peak 15 from + TIC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		4295	1.32					
54.0500		7952	2.45					
55.0600		87577	26.99					
56.0700		44933	13.85					
57.0700	1	324442	100.00					
58.0700	1	15379	4.74					
67.0500		18347	5.65					
68.0500		13677	4.22					
69.0700		73217	22.57					
70.0700		40937	12.62					
71.0800	1	248994	76.75					
72.0800	1	13935	4.30					
79.0400		7613	2.35					
81.0600		19217	5.92					
82.0600		19274	5.94					
83.0800		63386	19.54					
84.0800		27330	8.42					
85.0900	1	188778	58.19					
86.0900	1	13359	4.12					
91.0400		8513	2.62					
93.0500		7563	2.33					
95.0700		13687	4.22					
96.0700		13244	4.08					
97.0800		58236	17.95					
98.0900		20581	6.34					
99.1000	1	66942	20.63					
100.0900	1	6080	1.87					
105.0500		8061	2.48					
107.0700		6811	2.10					
109.0800		8351	2.57					
110.0800		6720	2.07					
111.1000		31219	9.62					
112.1000		15895	4.90					
113.1100	1	41224	12.71					
114.1100	1	3795	1.17					
119.0700		4915	1.51					
120.0600		3328	1.03					
121.0800		5981	1.84					
123.0900		5364	1.65					
124.1000		4444	1.37					
125.1100		15611	4.81					
126.1200		12884	3.97					
127.1300	1	29230	9.01					
128.0900	1	4667	1.44					
131.0700		3687	1.14					
133.0600		5267	1.62					
135.0800		5064	1.56					
138.1300		3557	1.10					
139.1200		6223	1.92					
140.1500		10426	3.21					
141.1400	1	23214	7.16					
142.1100	1	4065	1.25					
143.0700		3578	1.10					
145.0900		6589	2.03					
147.0900		7821	2.41					
153.1400		3690	1.14					
154.1600		8934	2.75					
155.1700		16135	4.97					
159.1000		3301	1.02					
168.1700		7482	2.31					
169.1800		12261	3.78					
182.1900		5966	1.84					
183.1900		9897	3.05					
196.2100		5169	1.59					
197.2000		8577	2.64					
207.0500		7320	2.26					
210.2300		4326	1.33					
211.2400		6988	2.15					
224.2500		3583	1.10					
225.2600		5609	1.73					
239.2600		5169	1.59					
253.2300		5293	1.63					
267.2700		4437	1.37					
281.2300		4957	1.53					
295.3300		3387	1.04					
396.3900		6575	2.03					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	75.05	75.05			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99BO3				2665-11-4	69.68	69.68			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	67.39	67.39			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	66.01	66.01			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideutero hexadecanol	C16H32D2O				56555-03-4	65.71	65.71			W11N17main.L

Analysis Report

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes	Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3	74764-11-7			75.05	75.05			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 73.651-73.932 min) Peak 16 from + TIC Scan (1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate; C17H34D2O3S)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0200		1912	5.94					
54.0200		1934	6.00					
55.0500		20179	62.65					
56.0500		5286	16.41					
57.0700		27405	85.08					
58.0300		3557	11.04					
59.0200		1413	4.39					
59.9900		1258	3.91					
67.0400		7783	24.16					
68.0400		3661	11.37					
69.0500		18475	57.36					
70.0500		4641	14.41					
71.0600	1	25469	79.07					
72.0500	1	1351	4.19					
73.0200	1	3557	11.04					
77.0100		2059	6.39					
79.0400		4352	13.51					
80.0300		2910	9.03					
81.0500		10121	31.42					
82.0500		4956	15.39					
83.0600		11296	35.07					
84.0400		4865	15.11					
85.0700	1	14179	44.02					
86.0500	1	1143	3.55					
91.0300		4978	15.45					
92.0300		1196	3.71					
93.0400		4816	14.95					
94.0400		2931	9.10					
95.0600		10428	32.37					
96.0500		4674	14.51					
97.0700		12044	37.39					
98.0600		5050	15.68					
99.0700		32211	100.00					
100.0400	1	31532	97.89					
101.0300	1	3181	9.88					
105.0400		3312	10.28					
107.0500		3659	11.36					
108.0600		2861	8.88					
109.0700		6762	20.99					
110.0700		2240	6.95					
111.0800		5966	18.52					
112.0600		2037	6.32					
113.0600		6775	21.03					
114.0400		3480	10.80					
115.0400		1767	5.49					
117.0100		1185	3.68					
119.0500		3515	10.91					
120.0400		1237	3.84					
121.0500		1692	5.25					
121.1000		2012	6.25					
122.0700		1821	5.65					
123.0800		5120	15.90					
124.0700		2498	7.76					
125.0900		3213	9.97					
126.0900		945	2.93					
127.0900		5111	15.87					
128.0500		1521	4.72					
129.0400		1597	4.96					
131.0500		1527	4.74					
133.0400		2753	8.55					
134.0600		2565	7.96					
135.0700		3869	12.01					
136.0500		1037	3.22					
137.0900		2632	8.17					
138.0900		5438	16.88					
139.0900		1798	5.58					
140.1100		988	3.07					
141.0900		13412	41.64					
142.0800		2601	8.07					
143.0500		1087	3.37					
145.0500		1261	3.91					
147.0600		2101	6.52					
149.0900		1958	6.08					
151.0800		1678	5.21					
155.1500		1010	3.14					
156.1100		16153	50.15					
157.1100		5613	17.43					
159.0900		982	3.05					
161.1100		971	3.01					
163.0800		1207	3.75					
165.0800		1344	4.17					
169.1100		5480	17.01					
173.1000		960	2.98					
175.0900		1106	3.43					
184.1300		1195	3.71					
189.1300		1407	4.37					
191.0500		1345	4.18					
197.1300		1069	3.32					
198.1500		1123	3.49					
201.1100		1036	3.22					
207.0400	1	7396	22.96					
208.0500	1	1731	5.38					
209.0400	1	1039	3.22					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
253.0600		1270	3.94					
281.0600		3271	10.16					
304.3100		1751	5.44					
323.3300		1082	3.36					
362.3900		1195	3.71					
365.3500		1858	5.77					
393.3800		1049	3.26					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	59.58	59.58			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Ethyl-4-[4-(2-ethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-4-yl)butyl]-1,3,2-dioxaborolane	C12H24B2O4				74793-62-7	59.04	59.04			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,3,2-Dioxaborolane, 4,4'-(1,4-butanediyl)bis[2-ethyl-	C12H24B2O4				74793-62-7	58.74	58.74			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideutero hexadecanol	C16H32D2O				56555-03-4	58.39	58.39			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	57.39	57.39			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes 1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S		56555-04-5			59.58	59.58			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 74.349-74.544 min) Peak 17 from + TIC Scan (Solanesol; C45H74O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		3319	13.16					
54.0200		1859	7.38					
55.0500		25211	100.00					
56.0500		6302	25.00					
57.0600	1	24586	97.52					
58.0400	1	1678	6.66					
60.0000		3175	12.59					
60.9900		2504	9.93					
65.0100		1356	5.38					
67.0400		13275	52.66					
68.0500		14943	59.27					
69.0600		24173	95.88					
70.0600		6053	24.01					
71.0700		16044	63.64					
73.0200		5741	22.77					
77.0200		3491	13.85					
78.0100		1208	4.79					
79.0400		9258	36.72					
80.0400		2896	11.49					
81.0600		20683	82.04					
82.0600		16702	66.25					
83.0700		17354	68.84					
84.0500		4094	16.24					
85.0800		8779	34.82					
91.0400		7626	30.25					
92.0300		1718	6.81					
93.0600		7946	31.52					
94.0600		4303	17.07					
95.0700		22499	89.24					
96.0700		9104	36.11					
97.0700		15099	59.89					
98.0600		3279	13.01					
99.0800		3057	12.13					
105.0400		7089	28.12					
106.0400		1804	7.16					
107.0600		7434	29.49					
108.0600		2861	11.35					
109.0700		11522	45.70					
110.0800		4730	18.76					
111.0900		8516	33.78					
112.0800		1844	7.32					
113.0800		1643	6.52					
115.0300		1935	7.67					
117.0300		2409	9.56					
119.0600		5439	21.58					
120.0600		2709	10.75					
121.0800		6682	26.51					
122.0700		3225	12.79					
123.1000		15481	61.41					
124.1000		7496	29.73					
125.1000		4750	18.84					
126.0900		1547	6.14					
127.0800		1628	6.46					
129.0600		3267	12.96					
131.0500		3719	14.75					
133.0600		5466	21.68					
134.0700		2384	9.46					
135.0800		5577	22.12					
136.0800		2444	9.70					
137.1000		4498	17.84					
138.1000		2346	9.30					
139.1000		1838	7.29					
141.0700		1771	7.03					
143.0800		1705	6.76					
145.0900		4126	16.37					
147.0800		4151	16.46					
148.0900		1190	4.72					
149.1000		2841	11.27					
151.0900		2860	11.34					
152.0800		1605	6.37					
153.1000		1231	4.88					
157.0900		2655	10.53					
158.1000		1676	6.65					
159.0900		3266	12.95					
160.0800		1246	4.94					
161.1100		3360	13.33					
163.0900		2312	9.17					
165.0900		1632	6.47					
171.0800		1713	6.80					
173.0800		1876	7.44					
175.1100		2366	9.38					
177.1000		1462	5.80					
185.1000		1270	5.04					
187.1000		1588	6.30					
189.1400		4882	19.36					
190.1400		1545	6.13					
191.0900		2179	8.64					
203.1500		1632	6.48					
207.0400		7416	29.42					
211.1100		1283	5.09					
211.1600		1263	5.01					
213.1600		2698	10.70					
229.1600		2047	8.12					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
253.1100		1880	7.46					
271.1900		2518	9.99					
278.2600		1208	4.79					
281.1100		4479	17.77					
296.2700		1234	4.89					
314.2400		1715	6.80					
314.2800		2172	8.62					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	68.11	68.11			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O				0-00-0	67.24	67.24			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O				0-00-0	66.65	66.65			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	10,10-Dimethyl-3-oxatricyclo[7.1.1.0]undecan-4-one	C12H18O2				0-00-0	66.48	66.48			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Nerolidol-epoxyacetate	C17H28O4				0-00-0	66.38	66.38			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Solanesol	C45H74O		0-00-0			68.11	68.11			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 74.544-74.733 min) Peak 18 from + TIC Scan (Solanesol; C45H74O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		2603	12.97					
54.0200		1507	7.51					
55.0500		20067	100.00					
56.0400		3977	19.82					
57.0600		17090	85.16					
60.0000		2242	11.17					
67.0400		10913	54.38					
68.0500		5776	28.79					
69.0600		16633	82.89					
70.0600		3732	18.60					
71.0700		12403	61.81					
73.0200		4634	23.09					
77.0200		4026	20.06					
78.0100		1382	6.89					
79.0400		9948	49.57					
80.0400		2399	11.95					
81.0500		16686	83.15					
82.0600		6869	34.23					
83.0600		10939	54.51					
84.0500		2630	13.10					
85.0800		6762	33.69					
91.0400		10872	54.18					
92.0500		2597	12.94					
93.0600		10772	53.68					
94.0500		3794	18.90					
95.0700		16742	83.43					
96.0600		5175	25.79					
97.0700		9880	49.23					
98.0500		2129	10.61					
99.0700		2453	12.22					
105.0500		11203	55.83					
106.0500		3022	15.06					
107.0700		11527	57.44					
108.0700		4103	20.45					
109.0700		10650	53.07					
110.0700		2838	14.14					
111.0800		5587	27.84					
115.0200		2171	10.82					
117.0400		3908	19.48					
118.0400		1726	8.60					
119.0600		8158	40.65					
120.0600		4747	23.66					
121.0700		8924	44.47					
122.0600		3102	15.46					
123.0900		7610	37.92					
124.0800		3273	16.31					
125.0900		3381	16.85					
128.0400		1687	8.41					
129.0500		3752	18.70					
131.0500		5310	26.46					
132.0400		1776	8.85					
133.0700		7658	38.16					
134.0700		3719	18.53					
135.0900		7783	38.79					
136.0900		2911	14.51					
137.1000		3284	16.37					
141.0900		1499	7.47					
143.0600		3997	19.92					
145.0800		8587	42.79					
146.0700		2492	12.42					
147.1000		7447	37.11					
148.0900		2455	12.23					
149.1100		4287	21.36					
151.1000		1926	9.60					
157.0700		3004	14.97					
158.0900		2287	11.40					
159.1000		5802	28.91					
160.0900		3152	15.71					
161.1100		5642	28.12					
163.1200		4560	22.72					
171.0900		2290	11.41					
173.1000		3081	15.35					
175.1200		2839	14.15					
177.1000		2307	11.49					
178.1000		1887	9.40					
185.1100		2084	10.39					
187.1200		2369	11.81					
189.1500		4782	23.83					
190.1500		1621	8.08					
191.1200		3184	15.87					
199.1200		2111	10.52					
203.1500		1776	8.85					
207.0500		7625	38.00					
213.1600		4991	24.87					
229.1600		1724	8.59					
231.1800		1992	9.93					
253.0400		1668	8.31					
255.1900		3591	17.89					
256.2100		1491	7.43					
261.2300		1677	8.36					
273.2100		2037	10.15					
281.0600		3329	16.59					
289.2900		3770	18.79					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
315.2900		3608	17.98					
367.3500		2642	13.17					
382.3800	1	5663	28.22					
383.3500	1	1839	9.16					
385.3600		2162	10.78					
400.3900	1	5752	28.66					
401.3900	1	1820	9.07					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	61.25	61.25			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O				0-00-0	59.91	59.91			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O				0-00-0	59.11	59.11			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Nerolidol-epoxyacetate	C17H28O4				0-00-0	57.52	57.52			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-(1-Hydroxymethylvinyl)-2-hydroxymethyl-3a,4-dimethylperhydroinden e	C15H24O2				0-00-0	56.76	56.76			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Solanesol	C45H74O		0-00-0			61.25	61.25			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

MassHunter Qual 10.0
(End of Report)